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ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CREDIT SCORING WITH THE RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM

JEL Classification: D22

SECTION “ECONOMICS”: Економіка

Abstract. The article deals with the economic efficiency of using the Random Forest algorithm in credit scoring systems. The study employs such general scientific methods as a graphical method to consider the structure of the banks' loan portfolio; comparison to determine the differences between traditional scoring and scoring through Random Forest; modelling to create a basic example of a scoring model based on the Random Forest algorithm using the Python libraries scikit-learn and matplotlib; synthesis to summarize theoretical approaches to scoring models and the results of empirical observations, in particular, when drawing conclusions about the advantages of the algorithm. The article reveals the essence of credit scoring, its role in reducing credit risk, and optimizing the process of assessing borrowers' creditworthiness. It is emphasized that the problem of credit risk forces banks to look for various ways and methods to reduce the impact of this risk to avoid lost profits and excessive losses because of the transformation of credit risk into real problem loans. The structure of the banks' loan portfolio for 2023 is considered and the leading banks in terms of loan disbursement are identified, namely Privatbank JSC, Oschadbank JSC, Ukrgasbank JSC, PUMB JSC, Ukreximbank JSC, ProCredit Bank JSC, and OTP Bank JSC. A comparative analysis of traditional credit scoring and scoring using the Random Forest algorithm is carried out. It is established that the use of credit scoring with Random Forest has certain advantages over traditional credit scoring. The author realised an example of modelling credit scoring with the Random Forest algorithm on artificially generated data, followed by a visual analysis of the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve and the importance of features, as well as the interpretation of model hyperparameters.

Keywords: credit risk, banking, loan portfolio, information technology, traditional scoring, machine learning algorithms.

Анотація. У статті розглядається економічна ефективність використання алгоритму Random Forest у системах кредитного скорингу. У дослідженні застосовано такі загальнонаукові методи, як графічний метод – для аналізу структури кредитного портфеля банків; метод порівняння – для виявлення відмінностей між традиційним скорингом і скорингом із використанням алгоритму Random Forest; метод моделювання – для побудови базового прикладу скорингової моделі на основі алгоритму Random Forest із використанням бібліотек Python (scikit-learn та matplotlib); метод синтезу – для узагальнення теоретичних підходів до побудови скорингових моделей і результатів емпіричних спостережень, зокрема при формулюванні висновків щодо переваг застосування зазначеного алгоритму. У статті розкрито суть кредитного скорингу, його роль у зниженні кредитного ризику та оптимізації процесу оцінювання

платоспроможності позичальників. Наголошено, що проблема кредитного ризику змушує банки шукати різні способи та методи зниження впливу цього ризику з метою уникнення втрат прибутку та надмірних збитків унаслідок трансформації кредитного ризику в реальні проблемні кредити. Проаналізовано структуру кредитного портфеля банків за 2023 рік та визначено провідні банки за обсягами виданих кредитів, зокрема: АТ «ПриватБанк», АТ «Ощадбанк», АБ «Укргазбанк», АТ «ПУМБ», АТ «Укркресімбанк», АТ «ПроКредит Банк» та АТ «ОТП Банк». Проведено порівняльний аналіз традиційного кредитного скорингу та скорингу з використанням алгоритму Random Forest. Встановлено, що використання скорингу з алгоритмом Random Forest має певні переваги над традиційними методами. Автором реалізовано приклад моделювання кредитного скорингу із застосуванням алгоритму Random Forest на штучно згенерованих даних, проведено візуальний аналіз кривої ROC, важливості ознак та інтерпретацію гіперпараметрів моделі.

Ключові слова: кредитний ризик, банківська справа, кредитний портфель, інформаційні технології, традиційний скоринг, алгоритми машинного навчання.

Introduction

The risks are an integral part of any business activity, including banking. Any credit organization faces several risks in its activities, but credit risk is the most critical and important of all. The most serious stage in lending is the assessment of creditworthiness. Competent determination of the creditworthiness of the clients enables banks to prematurely regulate and minimize credit risks. The development of information and computer technologies has made scoring the most popular and effective method of determining creditworthiness.

The assessment of the creditworthiness of individuals occupies a prominent place in current studies on banking and financial management. The study of L. Fedevych and V.N. Tsykvas examines on the role of the main financial and economic instruments in a market economy. It is focused on the importance of credit as a mechanism for optimizing social reproduction proportions. A rational distribution of finances between sectors of the economy is ensured by the effective use of credit resources, which contributes to its balanced development [1]. Other researchers N. Volkova and A. Shcherbata consider the role of the main financial and economic instruments in a market economy. Their study is focused on the importance of credit as an important element of the financial system, which ensures the optimization of social reproduction proportions [2]. At the same time, other researchers O. Stets and I. Lazarenko believe that in the era of globalization and rapid growth in information volumes, modern organizations are forced to quickly respond to changes in the market situation, increase the efficiency of their business processes, and seek new opportunities for the development and growth using modern digital technologies [3]. The article by B. Syrovertnyk, Ya. Kis and A. Khudyi considers credit risk in assessing the probability that a borrower will not fulfil his/her obligations to repay a loan or credit line. This process is key for financial institutions to make informed decisions in the field of lending and develop effective risk management strategies [4].

The relevance of the problem makes it appropriate to turn to international experience, in particular to the studies that analyse the effectiveness of credit scoring systems in different countries. For example, in his work, the scientist I. Rahman emphasizes that credit scoring plays a dominant role in the activities of financial institutions, serving as an effective tool for assessing the credit risk of clients. Its accuracy has a direct impact on the quality of risk management and the validity of decisions made in the field of lending [5]. The research by S.O. Kuyoro et al. proved that the Random Forest provides better accuracy of credit scoring and credit rating due to its classification power [6]. The study by D. Boughaci et al. studies the concepts of clusters in the development of credit scoring models. The authors developed an effective credit scoring model to improve the prediction of financial bankruptcy [7]. Other authors P. Ziemba, A. Radomska-Zalas and J. Becker consider the effectiveness of different combinations of classifiers and feature selection methods in credit risk assessment [8]. The V.P. Kumar's study shows how to classify customers who have

not paid off their credit card balances with a random forest algorithm using a data set containing credit card payment history [9].

So, some issues are poorly explored despite the large number of studies on credit scoring. It is not sufficiently studied how each algorithm — Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and XGBoost — changes the amount of savings for the bank due to the reduction of credit risks. Another understudied issue is promising scoring methods, such as neural networks or deep learning, which can provide even more accurate results for big data and unstable economic conditions. There is a need to focus on how the Random Forest algorithm copes with the assessment of the creditworthiness of small enterprises, where the data may be less structured.

The above aspects create opportunities for further research and improvement of credit scoring models, allowing banks to reduce risks, increase the accuracy of assessments and, ultimately, improve the economic efficiency of lending.

The aim of the study is to establish the impact of credit scoring using the Random Forest algorithm on the economic efficiency of banking institutions. The aim involves the fulfilment of the following research objectives:

1. Analyse the structure of the bank credit portfolio of Ukraine for 2023 with an emphasis on identifying lending leaders and determining the dynamics of the retail credit market.
2. Carry out a comparative analysis of traditional credit scoring and the Random Forest algorithm.
3. Realize a hypothetical example of credit scoring modelling using the Random Forest algorithm on artificially generated data, with subsequent visual analysis of the ROC curve and the importance of features, as well as interpretation of the model hyperparameters.

Results

The development of market relations in Ukraine, which began only in the 1990's, directly influenced the development of banks as independent commercial credit institutions. Ukrainian banks actively adapted to the new market conditions for the country and adopted many aspects of the work of Western banks. Such aspects included the assessment of the creditworthiness of a potential borrower, which is one of the necessary elements of the successful operation of any credit institution [10].

The problem of the credit risk forces banks to look for various ways and methods of reducing the impact of this risk to avoid lost profits and incur excessively large losses because of the transformation of credit risk into real non-performing loans. The concept of the borrower's creditworthiness and the need for its definition by banks becomes very important.

There is an urgent need to automate and optimize the traditional lending process, in which the decision to approve or reject a loan is made by a credit expert, as the bank is primarily interested in assessing the borrower's creditworthiness when issuing a loan to an individual. The practice of using creditworthiness assessment systems by banks shows that scoring systems are given much more authority in the decision-making process for relatively small loan amounts than for higher ones, where the scoring assessment is used more as a "support" factor considered by the credit expert.

Scoring is the assignment of points to a specific criterion and deriving a total credit rating based on the sum of all the assigned points, which gives grounds to conclude whether to grant a loan. In other words, credit scoring enables banks to make decisions about granting a loan more quickly. Any scoring system involves three main stages in its work: collecting information, analysing it, and issuing a result based on the analysis [11].

Information collection is the entry of all necessary data, criteria, and parameters specific to the borrower based on the documents provided by him/her, a completed questionnaire, and information from credit bureaus and some government agencies.

The analysis involves calculating the points for each criterion considering the weight (the importance) of a particular criterion for the bank. Each type of borrower is assigned a certain number of points and a certain status. The system processes all the borrower's data, considering a large number of parameters that

affect the borrower's assessment. All parameters are assigned their own point values and coefficients — weight coefficients that characterize the importance of the corresponding client parameters, as a result, all the points are summed up, and a scoring score is calculated.

Finally, at the last stage, all the points are summed up and a credit rating is displayed, which characterizes the borrower's creditworthiness and makes it possible to decide on issuing a loan to the client. So, the credit rating is calculated within a certain scale, in which the so-called “cut-offline” is set — the minimum threshold of points required to obtain a loan. Borrowers whose rating does not exceed this threshold are considered insufficiently reliable by banks and, as a rule, are excluded at the pre-selection stage [11].

One of the dynamically developing areas of banking in Ukraine is the retail segment of the credit market, which plays a significant role both for the banking sector and for the economy. So, its role for the population is to improve the quality of life by satisfying the need for goods and services at the expense of borrowed funds provided by the lending bank. The expansion of retail lending by banks contributes to attracting new clients, which is important from the perspective of replenishing the resources, as well as the development of additional services to the population in terms of issuing plastic cards, settlement and cash services, and other areas of servicing individuals [12].

The recent growth of the lending services market has been observed in Ukraine, which includes lending to individuals. General statistics on the lending market in Ukraine for 2023 indicate the restoration of credit activity. In 2023, banks issued 13,658 loans for ₴44.7 milliard [13]. In terms of the economic sectors, the largest number of loans, partially guaranteed by the state on a portfolio basis, are serviced in the following sectors: agriculture, wholesale and retail trade, vehicle repair, processing industry, transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities.

Figure 1 shows the structure of the bank's loan portfolio as of 2023.

Figure 1. Structure of the bank loan portfolio for 2023.

Source: compiled by the author based on [13]

So, according to the results of 2023, agriculture received 6,876 loans for a total amount of over ₴35 billion; wholesale and retail trade, vehicle repair – 6,973 loans for ₴15.3 billion; processing industry – 2,417 loans for ₴11.1 billion; transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities – 999 loans for ₴2.1 billion [13].

As of January 1, 2024, Privatbank JSC continues to serve the largest number of loans provided under state guarantees on a portfolio basis, Oschadbank JSC ranks second in terms of the number of such loans, and Ukrgasbank JSC ranks third [13].

Figure 2 presents the banks that provided the largest number of loans in 2023.

Figure 2. Banks that provided the largest number of loans in 2023

Source: compiled by the author based on [13]

So, Privatbank JSC supports 12,922 loans for a total amount of over €23.5 milliard; Oschadbank JSC — 2,719 loans for almost €10.9 milliard; JSC Ukrgasbank 713 loans for €8.1 milliard; PUMB JSC 527 loans for €5.3 milliard; Ukreximbank JSC 354 loans for €5.3 milliard; ProCredit Bank JSC — 548 loans for €3.4 milliard; OTP Bank — 287 loans for €2 milliard [13].

The presented data indicate positive trends in lending, which may be associated with the introduction of advanced analytical methods, such as Random Forest, for assessing credit risks. The growth of this market leads to an increase in the level of credit risks not only for individual organizations, but also for the entire banking system of the country.

Banks strive to constantly improve them and increase the quality and efficiency of scoring models by actively applying scoring methods in determining the creditworthiness of potential borrowers. Credit organizations constantly invest huge funds in the development of their own solutions in the field of credit scoring or actively implement developments and products of third-party companies offering similar services.

It is worth noting that the Random Forest algorithm is one of the most promising technologies in combination with artificial intelligence (AI) methods in current studies on credit scoring. Its application significantly increases the accuracy of predicting the borrowers' solvency and the overall effectiveness of scoring models in banking practice [14].

The Random Forest algorithm is one of the most powerful machine learning (ML) methods used to solve classification and regression problems. Its effectiveness is determined by the principle of ensemble — the combination of numerous decision trees, which ensures high accuracy and stability of results even in cases of noise in the data [14].

The essence of the algorithm is to build many decision trees, each working with a random subset of the input data and a random set of features. Each tree independently decides regarding the class (for example, “grant credit” or “reject”). After that, all the trees “vote”, and the final decision is made based on most votes. Credit scoring with Random Forest has certain advantages compared to traditional credit scoring. Table 1 presents a comparative characteristic of traditional credit scoring and scoring with the Random Forest algorithm.

Table 1

Comparison of traditional credit scoring and scoring with the Random Forest algorithm

Criteria	Traditional Credit Scoring	Credit Scoring with Random Forest
1	2	3
Evaluation method	Linear regression, logistic regression, statistical methods	Ensemble of decisions, decision tree, Random Forest
Model type	Linear or statistical models	Decision tree models, ensemble methods
Model complexity	Simple, good for simple data	More complex, can handle nonlinear relationships
Big data processing	Limited ability to handle large data sets	High ability to handle large and complex datasets
Result interpretation	Easy to interpret, easy to explain	Can be difficult to interpret (especially with large number of trees)
Processing time	Faster but less accurate for large data sets	Can be slower, but more accurate for large data
Resistance to overfitting	Slightly prone to overfitting on small data sets	Less prone to overfitting due to random selection of subsets of data and features
Flexibility and adaptation to new conditions	Limited flexibility, requires model re-adjustment	High flexibility, models can adapt to new conditions without significant re-adjustment
Feature importance analysis	Limited, depends on the method	High, Random Forest can estimate the importance of each feature
Adjustment complexity	Minimal adjustment, can use default parameters	Requires hyperparameter tuning, may take more time to optimize
Errors/accuracy	May have high error on complex data sets	Higher accuracy, reduced errors due to ensemble approach
Real-time use	Can be used for real-time, but with certain limitations	Can be used for real-time, although requires more resources

Source: compiled by the author based on [5;6]

So, the information in Table 1 shows the main differences between traditional credit scoring and the Random Forest-based approach. The Random Forest algorithm is more complex and powerful, which processes large amounts of data and reduce the risks of overfitting, but it requires more computational resources and more complex setup. However, despite these disadvantages, recent studies show that its use provides significant advantages. The following hyperparameters play an important role in the work of the Random Forest algorithm:

- estimators — the number of based estimators (trees) in the ensemble. Increasing this value improves accuracy, but takes more time;
- max_depth — the maximum depth of the tree. Helps to avoid overfitting;
- min_samples_split — the minimum number of examples for splitting a node;
- min_samples_leaf — the minimum number of examples in a leaf node;
- max_features — the number of features considered at each split;
- bootstrap — whether sampling with replacement is used to build each tree. Demonstration of the Random Forest model. Figure 3 below demonstrates the results of modelling the scoring system with the Random Forest algorithm are presented. The ROC curve demonstrates the ability of the model to distinguish reliable borrowers from unreliable ones.

Figure 3. ROC curve of the Random Forest model

Source: created by the author

So, the ROC curve indicates a high ability of the model to distinguish between reliable and risky borrowers, which is confirmed by the Area Under the Curve (AUC) value. The analysis of the importance of the features to assess the contribution of each parameter to the model's decision-making is carried out below.

Figure 4. Importance of features in the Random Forest model (hypothetical example)

Source: created by the author

So, the chart of the importance of features shows which characteristics have the greatest impact on decision-making. It is appropriate to give practical examples of using the method in this study. For example, in 2024, the research group Application of AI in Credit Risk Scoring for Small Business Loans from Azerbaijan conducted an analysis of the effectiveness of credit scoring models based on Random Forest, using real data from a local bank. They found that the classification accuracy increased from 81% (logistic regression) to 92%, and the number of overdue loans decreased by 18% after the implementation of the algorithm. This enabled the bank to save more than \$250 thousand in the first half year of using the system [15].

The researchers M. Thinesh et al. conducted a no less important work — Detection of Credit Card Fraud Using Random Forest Classification Model. They used the Random Forest algorithm to detect fraudulent transactions based on a real dataset from the Kaggle platform, where over 284 thousand transactions contained only 0.17% of fraud cases. After processing the data — in particular, scaling and dividing it into training and test samples — they built a model and assessed its quality using key metrics such as accuracy, completeness, F1-score, and ROC-AUC. As a result, the model showed better results than logistic regression due to its high completeness and overall reliability, especially in detecting rare fraudulent cases [16].

In their study Estimating Probability of Banking Crises Using Random Forest by S. Hartini et al., the researchers used the Random Forest algorithm to predict the probability of banking crises based on data from 79 countries for 1981-1999. The analysis comprised 11 economic indicators, including inflation, interest rates, GDP growth, capital flows, and the structure of bank assets. The model was trained on different sample proportions, and the highest accuracy — 98% — was achieved when using 90% of the data for training. High accuracy, sensitivity, and F1-measures demonstrated the effectiveness of Random Forest as a tool for early detection of financial threats to the banking system [17].

Conclusions

So, scoring methods are now considered the most effective tool for assessing the creditworthiness of both individuals and representatives of small and medium-sized businesses. The rational use of credit scoring enables banks to strengthen their positions in both the domestic and international markets, reduce the risks of losing reliable customers and promptly identify unreliable borrowers. Besides, the use of these methods opens prospects for the implementation of a unified identification system, biometric verification and the development of remote banking services.

A comparative analysis of traditional credit scoring and scoring based on the Random Forest algorithm was carried out in this study. The obtained results indicate the advantages of Random Forest in the context of bank lending. This algorithm demonstrates higher classification accuracy, the ability to detect nonlinear relationships between variables, reduced susceptibility to retraining, and high adaptability to new data. Despite the increased complexity of model setup and greater requirements for computational resources, Random Forest provides stable and reliable results, which is critical for credit risk management in the current environment.

The practical implementation of the credit scoring model with Random Forest visualized the efficiency of the algorithm through the ROC curve, which confirmed its high discriminatory ability. Analysis of the importance of features identified the most significant parameters that affect the model's decisions. This opens new opportunities for improving scoring systems and increasing the economic efficiency of banking institutions.

Further prospects for the study are the implementation of hybrid models using neural networks, which will further increase the accuracy of creditworthiness assessment, especially in cases of large amounts of data and an unstable economic environment.

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